

HOW DOES HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT MANAGE SUSTAINABLE ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN STARRED HOTELS IN BATAM CITY??

MAULI SIAGIAN¹, IDA AJU BRAHMASARI² and SITI MUJANAH³

¹Doctoral Program of Economics, Faculty of Economics & Business, Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya, Indonesia. Email: maulisgn@gmail.com

^{2,3}Lecturer, Faculty of Economics & Business, Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya, Indonesia.

Abstract

The hospitality sector in Batam plays a critical role in driving the local economy by increasing demand for accommodation, creating job opportunities, and improving residents' income. Collaboration with local vendors and craft industries supports the growth of local businesses. Despite challenges in maintaining service quality, hotel competition encourages innovation in services and facilities. By adapting to technological trends and sustainability, the hospitality sector remains a strong partner in sustainable and successful tourism development in Batam City. This study analyzes the effects of organizational culture, knowledge management practices, and organizational learning on human resource management practices (HRMP) and sustainable organizational performance in starred hotels in Batam City. The population of this study consisted of 557 employees working in starred hotels in Batam, with a sample of 233 employees. Data analysis was conducted using Structural Equation Modeling with AMOS 20. The findings indicate that organizational culture and knowledge management practices significantly affect HRMP, while organizational learning does not. Organizational culture does not have a significant direct effect on sustainable organizational performance. However, knowledge management practices and organizational learning positively contribute to sustainable performance. HRMP significantly affects sustainable organizational performance and mediates the effects of organizational culture and knowledge management practices on performance, although it does not mediate the effects of organizational learning. To enhance the performance of four- and five-star hotels in Batam City, the recommended steps include strengthening organizational culture with values of collaboration, innovation, and integrity; improving knowledge management through sharing and training platforms; optimizing organizational learning; advancing HRM practices focused on employee development and fair compensation; supporting career development and conflict resolution; and enhancing sustainable performance through product innovation, operational efficiency, and change management in a positive work environment.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Knowledge Management Practices, Organizational Learning, Human Resources Management Practices, Sustainable Organizational Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The hospitality sector is an essential component in supporting tourism by providing accommodations for travelers and playing a role in providing positive experiences. This sector contributes to the economy by creating employment opportunities and promoting destinations (Lee et al. 2016). Increased tourism activity also drives investments in tourism infrastructure development (Yu, Park, and Hyun 2021).

The COVID-19 pandemic led to a decline in hotel visits and occupancy. Although it started to recover in 2021, tourist visits in 2022 had not returned to pre-pandemic levels, though the upward trend is promising. Batam has 88 four- and five-star hotels with 11,044 rooms and

14,067 beds. The hospitality sector and tourism growth are mutually beneficial. Increasing tourist numbers drive demand for quality accommodations, while hotels provide essential resting places for visitors.

With innovation and quality service, hotels are essential partners in fostering tourism and local economic growth. A strong organizational culture focusing on hospitality and professionalism is essential to maintain service standards through employee development. Knowledge management practices (KMP) support human resource management practices (HRMP) by facilitating access to training information, career development, and best practices. Organizational learning enables HR to design effective training and ensure employees' access to the knowledge (Rasool et al. 2019). Performance evaluations and guest feedback allow hotels to improve HRMP continuously (Kordab, Raudeliūnienė, and Meidutė-Kavaliauskienė 2020). A positive organizational culture, effective knowledge management practices, and sustainable organizational learning support sustainable organizational performance.

Knowledge management practices improve hotel efficiency, reduce stress, and support career development. It creates a productive work environment, improves service quality, and boosts employee confidence (Jin et al. 2020). Knowledge management practices can be one of the key factors to deliver positive guest experiences and improve the hotel's image. Organizational support for sustainable learning and development can enhance HRM practices (Ulrich 2018).

An organizational culture aligned with sustainability goals in the hospitality industry can positively impact sustainable performance through socially responsible, environmentally friendly, and community-focused practices (Inthavong et al. 2023). Employees working in these environments are more likely to embrace sustainable practices. Additionally, a culture promoting integrity, transparency, and good business ethics can enhance guest trust and long-term investment (Sapta et al. 2021). The relationship between organizational culture and sustainable performance in hotels creates an environment where sustainable principles are consistently practiced for better outcomes.

Knowledge management practices and sustainable organizational performance have a significant impact (Valmohammadi, Sofiyabadi, and Kolahi 2019). Strong knowledge management practices support sustainable innovation by identifying opportunities for environmentally friendly solutions and socially responsible practices (Rasool et al. 2019). The integration of knowledge into hotel operations improves service quality, meets guest expectations, and supports sustainable performance (Sivagnanam et al. 2022). Effective organizational learning, including response to change and performance evaluation, improves efficiency and innovation (Paais and Pattiruhu 2020).

A strong organizational culture in starred hotels in Batam, combined with knowledge management practices, organizational learning, human resource management practices (HRMP), and sustainable organizational performance, creates a solid foundation for long-term success. The close relationship among these elements plays a crucial role in maintaining high standards in hotel services and performance. An organizational culture that reflects the values of service, hospitality, and professionalism serves as a foundation for implementing effective

HRMP, while a culture that supports collaboration and professional growth motivates employees to contribute to their full potential. Good HRMP, including recruitment, training, and employee development processes, provides support for maintaining high standards. Additionally, continuous organizational learning facilitates active performance evaluation, identification of improvement opportunities, and the implementation of changes. Organizational culture, knowledge management, and organizational learning contribute to enhancing market adaptation and sustainable performance. This study highlights the relationships among organizational culture, knowledge management, organizational learning, and sustainable organizational performance.

METHOD

This study employed an explanatory survey design as it explained the causal relationships between the independent variables—organizational culture, knowledge management practices, and organizational learning—and their effects on human resource management practices (HRMP) as an intervening variable, as well as their effects on sustainable organizational performance in starred hotels in Batam City. The data used in this study were derived from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data were obtained from the distribution of questionnaires to employees of four- and five-star hotels in Batam City. Meanwhile, secondary data were obtained from the Secretariat of BPP-PHRI (National Executive Board of the Indonesian Hotel and Restaurant Association) in Batam.

The research sample size was calculated using Slovin's formula based on a population of 557 employees, resulting in a sample of 233 respondents. The sampling technique employed was purposive sampling. The research instrument utilized was a questionnaire. Data analysis was conducted using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with Amos software version 20. The collected data were tabulated using descriptive statistics. This analysis described the mean and percentage as they are, without drawing conclusions regarding respondents' perceptions of the question indicators related to the research variables (Shajahan 2014). Subsequently, validity, reliability, and model testing were conducted.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

SEM Assumption Testing

In this study, the sample size used was 233, indicating that it met the sample adequacy requirements. Therefore, SEM could produce good and efficient estimates. The results of the normality test showed a multivariate c.r of -0.413, which was outside the range of -2.58 to +2.58 at a significance level of 5%. Therefore, it can be concluded that the multivariate data is normally distributed. The results of the univariate outlier test through the Z-score showed that the lowest Z-score value was -2.930, and the highest Z-score value was 1.916. Therefore, all indicators showed Z-Score values that were within the range of ± 3 . Therefore, it can be concluded that there were no univariate outliers in the research data. The results of the multivariate outlier detection showed that all observations had a mahalanobis d-squared value smaller than the maximum limit of the chi-square table of 72.05. Therefore, all observations

(respondents) were not indicated as outliers, and all could be used for further analysis. The detection of multicollinearity and singularity using the Amos program indicated that the correlation matrix among indicators (sample correlation matrix) produced the lowest value of -0.071 and the highest value of 0.753 (none exceeding 0.80). The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values for each independent variable were 1.036, 1.048, and 1.049, respectively, all three of which are less than 10. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity in this research model, and the assumptions of no multicollinearity or singularity can be met. Measurement model analysis was conducted simultaneously on all constructs.

The results of the goodness-of-fit test on the measurement model have produced the criteria that were met across absolute fit indices, incremental fit indices, and parsimony fit indices. Accordingly, the measurement model can be accepted as its fit was good (good fit or marginal fit). A good fit indicates a high level of model adequacy, while a marginal fit indicates an acceptable level of adequacy within tolerable limits. The results of the construct validity evaluation showed that all indicators in the measurement model had factor loading values greater than 0.50, confirming their validity in forming the constructs of organizational culture, knowledge management practices, organizational learning, human resource management practices, and sustainable organizational performance, thus meeting the criteria for convergent validity. Each variable also achieved construct reliability values exceeding 0.70, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values greater than 0.50. It can, therefore, be concluded that the indicators measuring the constructs of organizational culture, knowledge management practices, organizational learning, human resource management practices, and sustainable organizational performance are reliable and robust.

Structural Model Analysis

Similar to regression analysis, SEM also outputs the coefficient of determination (R^2). (Hair et al. 2018:152) states that the coefficient of determination measures the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables. The results of the calculation of the coefficient of determination (R^2) of the effect between variables in this study are presented in Table 8 below:

Table 1: Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The effects among variables	R^2
X1, X2, X3 \rightarrow Z	$R_Z^2 = 0.379$
X1, X2, X3, Z \rightarrow Y	$R_Y^2 = 0.465$
R^2 total = $1 - \sqrt{[(1-R_Z^2) \times (1-R_Y^2)]}$ = $1 - \sqrt{[(1-0.379) \times (1-0.465)]}$ = $1 - 0.576 = \mathbf{0.424}$	
Notes: X1: Organizational Culture X2: Knowledge Management Practices X3: Organizational Learning Z: Human Resource Management Practices (Z) Y: Sustainable Organizational Performance	

Table 1 shows that the value of R_{Z1}^2 is 0,379, meaning that the percentage of the effect of organizational culture, knowledge management practices, and organizational learning on human resource management practices at starred hotels in Batam City is 37.9 percent, while the remaining 62.1 percent is affected by other variables.

Furthermore, the R_Y^2 value is 0.465, meaning that the percentage of the effect of organizational culture, knowledge management practices, organizational learning, human resource management practices, and job satisfaction on sustainable organizational performance at starred hotels in Batam City is 46.5 percent, while the remaining 53.5 percent is affected by other variables.

The total coefficient of determination (R^2 total) is 0.424, indicating that the model developed in this study can explain about 42.2 percent of the data diversity. In other words, the model in this study has very good predictive relevance or is relevant to be used to predict sustainable organizational performance through organizational culture, knowledge management practices, organizational learning, and human resource management practice.

Figure 1: Summary of Parameter Significance Test Results

DISCUSSION OF VARIABLE DESCRIPTIVE RESULTS

The effect of organizational culture on human resource management practices

The research results and hypothesis testing using SEM found that the estimated coefficient of the effect of organizational culture on human resource management practices is significant with a CR value of 5.572 (greater than the 1.96 threshold) and a significance value (p -value) of 0.000 (less than the 5% threshold). The results of this hypothesis testing show that a strong and positive organizational culture tends to create an environment in which human resource

management practices (HRMP) can flourish. Employees engaged in a culture that encourages collaboration, open communication, and personal growth are more likely to experience greater support from management in terms of career development, training, and performance management. The results of this study are consistent with previous studies (Noe et al. 2019:309) (Wright 2020:207) (Wesson 2018:481) that organizational culture is highly diverse and unique, formed by the values and beliefs of the founder or leader or through implemented human resource management practices. This culture has a significant impact on the long-term success of the organization, making its management and development an important focus in organizational management. This is supported by previous research (Al-Bahussin and Elgaraihy 2013) (Schein 2010) (Quinn 2011) that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on human resource management practices.

The effect of knowledge management practices on human resource management practices

The coefficient estimation results for the effect of knowledge management practices on human resource management practices also show a significant effect with a CR value of 4.065 (greater than the 1.96 threshold) and a significance value (p -value) of 0.000 (less than the 5% threshold). The results of testing this hypothesis show that effective knowledge management practices can improve the efficiency and effectiveness of HRMP. A good system for sharing knowledge and experience enables HRMP to more easily identify employee training needs, manage organizational knowledge, and support innovation. The results of this study are consistent with the statements of previous studies (Kay 2018:347) (Hubert 2011:380) (Parcell 2001:309) that knowledge management practices recognize human resource management as one of an organization's most valuable assets. Therefore, it must be managed properly to increase productivity, efficiency, and organizational adaptability to environmental changes to obtain sustainable organizational performance. This conclusion is further corroborated by previous studies (Sunanda 2022) (Wood et al. 2019), which confirm that knowledge management practices have a positive and significant effect on human resource management practices.

The effect of organizational learning on human resource management practices

The coefficient estimation results for the effect of organizational learning on human resource management practices show an insignificant effect with a CR value of 1.119 (less than the 1.96 threshold) and a significance value (p -value) of 0.263 (greater than the 5% threshold). The results of this hypothesis testing show that although organizational learning is important for overall organizational development, the focus and objectives of organizational learning are considered to be more related to improving overall organizational performance than to specific management related to human resources. In the context of employees of 4- and 5-star hotels in Batam City, HRMP is more affected by internal factors specific to the hospitality industry, such as company policies. The results of this study are inconsistent with the assertions made by previous researchers (McLain, Chris, and Robert 2001:379), (Gold 2017:229), that learning organizations systematically collect data and information from various sources, including human resource practices, operational experience, customers, competitors, research, and internal input. The results also do not align with previous studies (Kokkaew, Peansupap, and

Jokkaw 2022) (Velsor 2019) that organizational learning has a significant effect on human resource management practices.

The effect of organizational culture on sustainable organizational performance

The coefficient estimation results for the effect of organizational culture on sustainable organizational performance show an insignificant effect with a CR value of 0.262 (less than the 1.96 threshold) and a significance value (p -value) of 0.793 (greater than the 5% threshold). The results of this hypothesis testing show that although a strong organizational culture can be the foundation for sustainable performance, external factors and other management practices are considered more instrumental in determining sustainable performance, especially in the hospitality industry. This is because sustainable organizational performance is highly affected by external factors such as tourism trends, market competition, and government regulations. The results of this study are inconsistent with the statements of previous researchers (Gold 2017:229), (Aswathappa 2020:307), (Sidani 2019:261), that organizational culture can have a significant impact on organizational performance and success. Organizational culture plays an important role in achieving sustainable performance. The results also do not align with studies by (Imran et al. 2021) (Hofstede 2001), who found that organizational culture has a significant effect on sustainable organizational performance.

The effect of knowledge management practices on sustainable organizational performance

The coefficient estimation results for the effect of knowledge management practices on sustainable organizational performance show a significant effect with a CR value of 4.171 (greater than the 1.96 threshold) and a significance value (p -value) of 0.000 (less than the 5% threshold). The results of this hypothesis testing show that efficiency in knowledge and information management can increase innovation, operational efficiency, and the organization's ability to adapt to change. All of which are critical factors in achieving sustainable organizational performance. The results of this study are consistent with the statements of previous researchers (Aswathappa 2020:307) (Prusak 2000:404) (Gold 2017:229) that knowledge management practices are essential for sustainable organizational performance because by managing knowledge effectively, organizations can increase productivity, innovation, and adaptation to change. This creates operational efficiency, supports continuous learning, and strengthens organizational competitiveness, all of which contribute to sustainable performance. This is supported by previous studies conducted (Valmohammadi et al. 2019), (Girard and McNeilly 2019), that knowledge management practices have a significant effect on sustainable organizational performance.

The effect of organizational learning on sustainable organizational performance

The coefficient estimation results for the effect of organizational learning on sustainable organizational performance also show a significant effect with a CR value of 3.374 (greater than the 1.96 threshold) and a significance value (p -value) of 0.000 (less than the 5% threshold). The results of this hypothesis testing show that effective organizational learning enables organizations to adapt quickly to environmental changes, avoid repeated mistakes, and improve

the ability to identify and capture new opportunities. All of which are crucial aspects of sustainable performance. The results of this study are consistent with the previous studies (Argote 2011:266) (Gold 2017:229) that organizational learning is closely related to sustainable organizational performance. It facilitates the continuous development of skills, adaptability, and innovation, thereby supporting long-term objectives and sustainable outcomes. The findings are also consistent with previous studies (Kordab et al. 2020) (Parcell 2001) (Kokkaew et al. 2022) that organizational learning has a significant effect on sustainable organizational performance.

The effect of human resource management practices on sustainable organizational performance

The coefficient estimation results for the effect of human resource management practices on sustainable organizational performance show a significant effect with a CR value of 3.166 (greater than the 1.96 threshold) and a significance value (*p*-value) of 0.002 (less than the 5% threshold). The results of this hypothesis testing show that effective human resource management practices, such as employee development, good performance management, and proper recruitment, can increase productivity, employee retention, and innovation, which in turn contribute to sustainable performance. The results of this study are consistent with the statements made by previous researchers (Aswathappa 2020:442), (Razzetti 2022:104), (Dessler 2020:344), (Sidani 2019:204), that effective HR practices—including recruitment, training, career development, and retention—positively impact long-term organizational performance. The findings also align with studies by previous studies (Rasool et al. 2019), (Russell Clavey 2013), (Weber 2006), that human resource management practices have a significant effect on sustainable organizational performance.

The effect of organizational culture (X1) mediated by human resource management practices (Z1) on sustainable organizational performance (Y)

The results of the indirect significance test for the pathway $X1 \rightarrow Z1 \rightarrow Y$ indicate a significant effect, with a positive coefficient of 0.065 and a significance value (*p*-value) of 0.043 (less than the 5% threshold). These findings suggest that HRMP significantly mediates the effect of knowledge management practices on sustainable organizational performance. This means that in the context of starred hotels in Batam City, HRMP plays a crucial role in translating the values and norms of organizational culture into practices that lead to sustainable organizational performance.

Therefore, to improve sustainable performance, starred hotels should not only focus on developing a strong organizational culture but also ensure the proper adoption of HRMP. The results of this study are consistent with previous studies (Gold 2017:229), (Aswathappa 2020:307), which show that effective HR management, including employee development, facilitates the implementation of knowledge management practices. This creates an environment where knowledge can be identified, shared, and utilized optimally, thereby improving overall organizational performance. However, no prior studies have explicitly addressed this specific mediation relationship.

The effect of knowledge management practices (X2) mediated by human resource management practices (Z1) on sustainable organizational performance (Y)

The results of the indirect significance test for the pathway $X2 \rightarrow Z1 \rightarrow Y$ also indicate a significant effect, with a positive coefficient of 0.065 and a significance value (p -value) of 0.043 (less than the 5% threshold). This indicates that HRMP significantly mediates the impact of knowledge management practices on sustainable organizational performance. Specifically, in the context of four- and five-star hotels in Batam City, effective knowledge management enhances sustainable performance, particularly when accompanied by robust HRMP practices. Starred hotels should, therefore, pay attention not only to the knowledge management aspect but also ensure that their HRMP system supports the application of such knowledge in daily practice. The results of this study are consistent with previous studies (Aswathappa 2020:307) (Gold 2017:229), which highlight that effective human resource management—particularly employee development—can facilitate the implementation of knowledge management practices. This creates an environment where knowledge can be identified, shared, and utilized optimally, ultimately improving organizational performance. However, no prior research has specifically examined this mediation effect.

The effect of organizational learning (X3) mediated by human resource management practices (Z1) on sustainable organizational performance (Y)

The results of the indirect significance test for the pathway $X3 \rightarrow Z1 \rightarrow Y$ show an insignificant effect with a coefficient value of only 0.017 and a significance value (p -value) of 0.576 (greater than the 5% threshold). This demonstrates that HRMP does not mediate the relationship between organizational learning and sustainable organizational performance. It indicates that in starred hotels in Batam City, organizational ability to learn is not significantly affected by HRMP practices in achieving sustainable performance. For hotels to improve their sustainable performance, the focus on developing organizational learning capabilities does not need to be exclusively accompanied by HRMP improvements. The results of this study are inconsistent with the statements of previous studies (Aswathappa 2020:307) (Gold 2017:229) that HR practices such as training and employee development can facilitate effective organizational learning processes. These processes create an environment where organizations can continuously learn, adapt, and enhance sustainable performance. However, this specific mediation effect has not been examined in previous studies.

Theoretical Findings

The theoretical findings in this study indicate that organizational culture has a significant effect on human resource management practices (HRMP), where the stronger the organizational culture, the better the HRMP. Knowledge management practices also have a positive effect on HRMP, while organizational learning does not have a significant effect on HRMP. HRMP has a significant effect on sustainable organizational performance. HRMP also mediates the effect of organizational culture and knowledge management practices on sustainable performance but does not mediate the effect of organizational learning.

Practical Findings

This study shows that four and five-star hotels in Batam City excel in organizational culture, knowledge management practices, organizational learning, and human resource management practices. Organizational culture is strong, especially in values, norms, and performance; however, rituals and traditions require updates. The knowledge management system is effective, although employee capability development requires attention. Organizational learning is supported by leadership and participation but needs to accelerate adaptation to change. Human resource management practices are good, with a focus on resolving complaints. Sustainable performance is achieved, but innovation and operational efficiency must be improved.

CONCLUSION

Organizational culture and knowledge management practices significantly affect HRMP, while organizational learning does not. Knowledge management practices and organizational learning have a positive effect on sustainable organizational performance. Although organizational culture and job satisfaction are not significantly affected, knowledge management practices, organizational learning, and HRMP have a positive effect. HRMP significantly affects sustainable performance and mediates the impact of organizational culture and knowledge management practices on sustainable performance but does not mediate the influence of organizational learning.

Suggestion

To enhance the performance of four- and five-star hotels in Batam City, the following steps are recommended: strengthening organizational culture with values of collaboration, innovation, and integrity; improving knowledge management through sharing platforms, training, and mentoring; optimizing organizational learning with relevant development programs; improving HRMP with a focus on employee development, performance management, and fair compensation, and routinely evaluating these practices; providing career development opportunities and effective conflict resolution mechanisms; optimizing sustainable performance through product innovation, operational efficiency, and change management; and managing organizational climate to create a positive and supportive work environment.

References

- 1) Abdalla, Khalifa, Rahouma Kashtia, and Pradhyuman Singh Lakhawat. 2017. "A Review Study on Human Resource Practices and Their Impact on Organizational Performance." 19(10):33–40. doi: 10.9790/487X-1910083340.
- 2) Al-Bahussin, Sami Abdullah, and Wael Hassan Elgaraihy. 2013. "The Impact of Human Resource Management Practices, Organisational Culture, Organisational Innovation and Knowledge Management on Organisational Performance in Large Saudi Organisations: Structural Equation Modeling With Conceptual Framework." *International Journal of Business and Management* 8(22):1–19. doi: 10.5539/ijbm.v8n22p1.
- 3) Argote, Linda. 2011. *Organizational Learning: Creating, Retaining and Transferring Knowledge*. Springer.

- 4) Aswathappa, K. 2020. *Human Resource Management: Text and Cases*. Tata McGraw-Hill Education.
- 5) Berman, Evan M., James S. Bowman, and Jonathan P. West Montgomery R. Van Wart. 2019. *Human Resource Management in Public Service: Paradoxes, Processes, and Problems*. Thousand Oaks: CQ Press.
- 6) Božović, Jelena, Ivan Božović, and Isidora Ljumović. 2019. "Impact of HRM Practices on Job Satisfaction of Employees in Serbian Banking Sector." *Management: Journal of Sustainable Business and Management Solutions in Emerging Economies* 24(1):63. doi: 10.7595/management.fon.2018.0035.
- 7) Dessler, Gary. 2020. *Human Resource Management*. Pearson.
- 8) Al Doghan, Mohammed A., Muhammad Awais Bhatti, and Ariff Syah Juhari. 2019. "Do Psychological Diversity Climate, HRM Practices, and Personality Traits (Big Five) Influence Multicultural Workforce Job Satisfaction and Performance? Current Scenario, Literature Gap, and Future Research Directions." *SAGE Open* 9(2). doi: 10.1177/2158244019851578.
- 9) Girard, John J. Girard Joann, and Mark McNeilly. 2019. *Knowledge Management: A Theoretical and Practical Guide for Knowledge Management in Your Organization*. CRC Press.
- 10) Gold, John Bratton Jeffrey. 2017. *Human Resource Management: Theory and Practice*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- 11) Hofstede, Geert. 2001. *Culture's Consequences: Comparing Values, Behaviors, Institutions and Organizations Across Nations*. Sage Publications.
- 12) Hubert, Carla O'Dell Cindy. 2011. *The New Edge in Knowledge: How Knowledge Management Is Changing the Way We Do Business*. Wiley.
- 13) Hussin, Norhayati, and Siti Hajar Mohd Mokhtar. 2018. "The Impacts of Knowledge Management Practices on Employees' Job Satisfaction." *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development* 7(3):338–51. doi: 10.6007/ijarped/v7-i3/4371.
- 14) Al Idrus, Salim, Ansari Saleh Ahmar, and Abdussakir. 2018. "The Effect of Organizational Learning on Market Orientation Moderated by Job Satisfaction." *Cogent Business and Management* 5(1):1–12. doi: 10.1080/23311975.2018.1475048.
- 15) Ijigu, Amare Werku. 2015. "The Effect of Selected Human Resource Management Practices on Employees' Job Satisfaction in Ethiopian Public Banks." *EMAJ: Emerging Markets Journal* 5(1):1–16. doi: 10.5195/emaj.2015.64.
- 16) Imran, Muhammad, Fadillah Binti Ismail, Khawar Hussain, Pratik Kumar Singh, and Abdul Aziz Ansari. 2021. "Achieving Sustainable Organisational Performance through Employee Job Satisfaction and Organizational Culture." *Psychology and Education Journal* 58(1):3089–3108. doi: 10.17762/pae.v58i1.1213.
- 17) Inthavong, Phoungphaynome, Khaliq Ur Rehman, Khansa Masood, Zeeshan Shaukat, Anna Hnydiuk-Stefan, and Samrat Ray. 2023. "Impact of Organizational Learning on Sustainable Firm Performance: Intervening Effect of Organizational Networking and Innovation." *Heliyon* 9(5):e16177. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16177.
- 18) Irwan, Andi, Mahfudnurnajamuddin Mahfudnurnajamuddin, Syamsu Nujum, and Suriyanti Mangkona. 2020. "The Effect of Leadership Style, Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance Mediated by Job Satisfaction." *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding* 7(8):642. doi: 10.18415/ijmmu.v7i8.2007.
- 19) Jeet, Vikram. 2014. "A Study of HRM Practices and Its Impact on Employees Job Satisfaction in Private Sector Banks: A Case Study of HDFC Bank." *International Journal of Advance Research in Computer Science and Management Studies* 2(1):62–68.

- 20) Jin, Jong Chol, Song Nam Hong, Guang Son Li, and Nam Ung Kim. 2020. "The Method of Evaluating Impacts of Knowledge Management on Job Satisfaction and Intellectual Level of Work." *International Journal of Knowledge Management* 16(4):42–62. doi: 10.4018/IJKM.2020100103.
- 21) Judge, Stephen P. Robbins, and Timothy A. 2022. *Organizational Behavior; Multiple Editions*. Pearson.
- 22) Kay, Paul Banfield Rebecca. 2018. *Human Resource Management in Practice: A Research-Based Approach*. Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD).
- 23) Khan, Hira, and Rafique Ahmed Khan. 2017. "Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Employee Job Satisfaction At Meezan Bank Limited, Karachi." *Journal of Business Administration and Management Sciences* 2(1):195–204.
- 24) Khan, Muhammad Asad, Fadillah Binti Ismail, Altaf Hussain, and Basheer Alghazali. 2020. "The Interplay of Leadership Styles, Innovative Work Behavior, Organizational Culture, and Organizational Citizenship Behavior." *SAGE Open* 10(1). doi: 10.1177/2158244019898264.
- 25) Kokkaew, Nakhon, Vachara Peansupap, and Noppadon Jokkaw. 2022. "An Empirical Examination of Knowledge Management and Organizational Learning as Mediating Variables between HRM and Sustainable Organizational Performance." *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 14(20). doi: 10.3390/su142013351.
- 26) Kordab, Mirna, Jurgita Raudeliūnienė, and Ieva Meidutė-Kavaliauskienė. 2020. "Mediating Role of Knowledge Management in the Relationship between Organizational Learning and Sustainable Organizational Performance." *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 12(23):1–20. doi: 10.3390/su122310061.
- 27) Lee, Soomi, Kelly D. Davis, Claudia Neuendorf, Alicia Grandey, Chun Bun Lam, and David M. Almeida. 2016. "Individual- and Organization-Level Work-to-Family Spillover Are Uniquely Associated with Hotel Managers' Work Exhaustion and Satisfaction." *Frontiers in Psychology* 7(AUG):1–12. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01180.
- 28) Mat Desa, Nasina, Muhammad Hasmi Abu Hassan Asaari, and Chiew Lee Yim. 2020. "Human Resource Management Practices and Job Satisfaction among Courier Service Provider Employees." *International Journal of Asian Social Science* 10(6):327–38. doi: 10.18488/journal.1.2020.106.327.338.
- 29) McLain, Smith Putnam, Argyris Chris, and Diana Robert. 2001. *Organizational Learning II: Theory, Method, and Practice*. Addison-Wesley Publishing Company.
- 30) Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart, and Wright. 2019. *Fundamentals of Human Resource Management*. New York: McGraw-Hill Education.
- 31) Noercahyo, Unggul Sentanu, Mohammad Syamsul Maarif, and I. Made Sumertajaya. 2021. "The Role of Employee Engagement on Job Satisfaction and Its Effect on Organizational Performance." *Jurnal Aplikasi Manajemen* 19(2):296–309. doi: 10.21776/ub.jam.2021.019.02.06.
- 32) Nurlina, N. 2022. "Examining Linkage Between Transactional Leadership, Organizational Culture, Commitment and Compensation on Work Satisfaction and Performance." *Golden Ratio of Human Resource Management* 2(2):108–22. doi: 10.52970/grhrm.v2i2.182.
- 33) Olaimat, Daifallah. 2018. "The Influence of Human Resource Practices on Job Satisfaction: Empirical Investigation of Jordan Hotels." *International Journal of Human Resource Studies* 8(4):136. doi: 10.5296/ijhrs.v8i4.13644.
- 34) Paais, Maartje, and Jozef R. Pattiruhu. 2020. "Effect of Motivation, Leadership, and Organizational Culture on Satisfaction and Employee Performance." *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business* 7(8):577–88. doi: 10.13106/JAFEB.2020.VOL7.NO8.577.
- 35) Parcell, Chris Collison Geoff. 2001. *Learning to Fly: Practical Lessons from One of the World's Leading Knowledge Companies*. Capstone.

- 36) Park, Jeong Eun, and Eungoo Kang. 2022. "The Mediating Role of Eco-Friendly Artwork for Urban Hotels to Attract Environmental Educated Consumers." *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 14(7). doi: 10.3390/su14073784.
- 37) Prusak, Thomas H. Davenport Laurence. 2000. *Working Knowledge: How Organizations Manage What They Know*. Harvard Business Review Press.
- 38) Quinn, Cameron dan. 2011. *Diagnosing and Changing Organizational Culture: Based on the Competing Values Framework*. 2011.
- 39) Rahman, Azizur, and Najmul Hasan. 2017. "Modeling Effects of KM and HRM Processes to the Organizational Performance and Employee's Job Satisfaction." *International Journal of Business and Management* 12(7):35. doi: 10.5539/ijbm.v12n7p35.
- 40) Rasool, Samma Faiz, Madeeha Samma, Mansi Wang, Yan Zhao, and Yanping Zhang. 2019. "How Human Resource Management Practices Translate into Sustainable Organizational Performance: The Mediating Role of Product, Process and Knowledge Innovation." *Psychology Research and Behavior Management* 12:1009–25. doi: 10.2147/PRBM.S204662.
- 41) Razzetti, Gustavo. 2022. *Remote Not Distant: Design a Company Culture That Will Help You Thrive in a Hybrid Workplace*. San Francisco: Hybrid Workplace Academy.
- 42) Ruiz-Palomino, Pablo, Benito Yáñez-Araque, Pedro Jiménez-Estévez, and Santiago Gutiérrez-Broncano. 2022. "Can Servant Leadership Prevent Hotel Employee Depression during the COVID-19 Pandemic? A Mediating and Multigroup Analysis." *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 174. doi: 10.1016/j.techfore.2021.121192.
- 43) Russell Clavey. 2013. *Sustainability in the Hospitality Industry: Principles of Sustainable Operations*. Routledge.
- 44) Sapta, I. Ketut Setia, I. Nengah Sudja, I. Nengah Landra, and Ni Wayan Rustiarini. 2021. "Sustainability Performance of Organization: Mediating Role of Knowledge Management." *Economies* 9(3):1–16. doi: 10.3390/economies9030097.
- 45) Sarker, Md. Atiqur Rahman, and Rumana Afroze. 2014. "Can HRM Practices Improve Job Satisfaction of Ready Made Garment (RMG) Workers in Bangladesh? An Alternative Solution to Recent Unrest." *International Journal of Business and Management* 9(10):185–94. doi: 10.5539/ijbm.v9n10p185.
- 46) Schein, Edgar H. 2010. *Organizational Culture and Leadership*. John Wiley & Sons.
- 47) Shajahan, S. 2014. *Introduction to Business Research Methods*. Jaico Publishing House.
- 48) Sidani, Tamer Cavusgil David M. DePew Yusuf. 2019. *Human Resource Management: People, Data, and Analytics*. Routledge.
- 49) Sivagnanam, Pavithra, Arul Ramanatha Pillai, Rajesh Elangovan, and Satyanarayana Parayitam. 2022. "Knowledge Management Process, Infrastructure, and System Quality as Resilient Strategies to Respond to COVID-19 Pandemic Challenges: Evidence from Higher Educational Institutions in India." *Knowledge and Process Management* (May). doi: 10.1002/kpm.1722.
- 50) Sunanda, Dr. K. 2022. "Human Resource Management Practices and Knowledge Management - a Study With Structural Equation Modelling Technique." *Interantional Journal of Scientific Research in Engineering and Management* 06(08):1–15. doi: 10.55041/ijrsrem13220.
- 51) Ulrich, Arthur K. Yeung and Dave. 2018. *Organizational Learning and Performance: The Science and Practice of Building a Learning Culture*. Oxford University Press.
- 52) Ulrich, Dave, Jon Younger, Wayne Brockbank, and Mike Ulrich. 2012. *HR from the Outside In: Six Competencies for the Future of Human Resources*. New York: McGraw-Hill Education.

- 53) Valmohammadi, Changiz, Javad Sofiyabadi, and Bahare Kolahi. 2019. "How Do Knowledge Management Practices Affect Sustainable Balanced Performance? Mediating Role of Innovation Practices." *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 11(18). doi: 10.3390/su11185129.
- 54) Velsor, Ryan Smerek Ellen Van. 2019. *Organizational Learning and Performance: The Science and Practice of Building a Learning Culture*. Jossey-Bass.
- 55) Virgana, Virgana, and Soeparlan Kasyadi. 2020. "The Effect of Organizational Culture, Personality, Job Satisfaction, and Trust on School Supervisor Performance." *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)* 14(3):434–41. doi: 10.11591/edulearn.v14i3.16408.
- 56) Weber, Andrew W. Savitz Karl. 2006. *The Triple Bottom Line: How Today's Best-Run Companies Are Achieving Economic, Social and Environmental Success - And How You Can Too*. Jossey-Bass.
- 57) Wesson, Jason A. Colquitt Jeffery A. Lepine Michael J. 2018. *Organizational Behavior: Improving Performance and Commitment in the Workplace*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- 58) Wood, Alex J., Mark Graham, Vili Lehdonvirta, and Isis Hjorth. 2019. "Networked but Commodified: The (Dis)Embeddedness of Digital Labour in the Gig Economy." *Sociology* 53(5):931–50. doi: 10.1177/0038038519828906.
- 59) Wright, Raymond A. Noe John R. Hollenbeck Barry Gerhart Patrick M. 2020. *Human Resource Management: Gaining a Competitive Advantage*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- 60) Yu, Jongsik, Junghyun Park, and Sunghyup Sean Hyun. 2021. "Impacts of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Employees' Work Stress, Well-Being, Mental Health, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Employee-Customer Identification." *Journal of Hospitality Marketing and Management* 30(5):529–48. doi: 10.1080/19368623.2021.1867283.